

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: *The article discusses in detail the concepts of the human factor, innovation and education. The role of human capital in the higher education system is also investigated.*

Keywords: *society, person, higher education, innovation, educational efficiency.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА И РОЛЬ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: *В статье подробно рассматриваются концепции человеческого фактора, инноваций и образования. Также исследована роль человеческого капитала в системе высшего образования.*

Ключевые слова: *общество, человек, высшее образование, инновации, образовательная эффективность.*

INTRODUCTION

On October 8, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PF-5847 on "Approving the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. According to him, "The following are the strategic goals of the development of the higher education system:

to improve the quality of training of highly qualified personnel for modernization of the country, sustainable socio-economic development, development of human capital based on the requirements of the labor market;" [1.] with this, the need to transform human capital with the development of society begins to be met.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovative Activities" dated July 24, 2020 №. O 'RQ-630, "Innovative development strategies are based on modern achievements of world science, innovative developments and technologies, rapid development of human capital, the country, and a unified state policy in the field of innovative activities" will be developed and implemented in order to go" [2.]. Therefore, it is urgent to increase the need to positively influence the development of society through the development of human capital. This is reflected in the experience of Finland. For example, "Innovation is not only the creation and improvement of technology for the production of goods and services. Innovation can also be social: solutions implemented during practice and contributing to people's participation in society usually increase wealth and health, education and well-being.

In the philosophy of education, specific renewal processes also affect human capital. In particular, according to the researcher, "The change of national culture under the influence of globalization will undoubtedly undermine the foundations of statehood and independence. This process requires an effective educational system to perform a protective function in preserving the moral image of the nation", [3.16.] he states.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Expanding the concept of "innovation" is a good and correct idea. Our well-being is based not only on the introduction and implementation of new technical solutions, but also on the

development and progress of society"[4.7.]. It is determined that the development of society depends on the activity of people with innovative ideas.

In order for the impact of human capital on the development of society to be only positive, the existing society should be free from vices such as corruption, lobbying and nihilism. Because, "...schooling, spending on medical care, lectures on the virtues of accuracy and honesty are also capital. This is because they increase income, improve health or extend a person's life. Therefore, economists consider spending on education, training, medical care, etc. as investments in human capital"[5.].

DISCUSSION

In this regard, the mechanisms of elimination of evils in the society should work systematically. Systematic work is being carried out in this regard as well. It is worth paying attention to the following phrase inscribed on the facade of Stellenbosch University, Republic of South Africa. "It does not take an atomic bomb or a long-range missile to destroy any nation. It is enough to reduce the quality of education and cheat in exams. Patients die at the hands of doctors trained in this way, houses and buildings built by builders are destroyed, financial resources are squandered at the hands of economists and accountants, and justice suffers at the hands of such lawyers and judges. "The crisis of education is the crisis of the nation."

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is clear from this that while reforms in the field of education appear as a factor indicating the efficiency of human capital, the factor that causes its disappearance is the scourge of corruption. The role of human capital development and higher education in society is to make the field of higher education a "corruption-free field" and to organize comprehensive measures[6.] to eliminate law violations and deficiencies.

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